

Formation and stability of transition metal chelates with 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzoxazole and other ligands

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Abstract : The formation equilibria of (1 : 1 and 1 : 2) binary chelates, ML and ML₂ and (1 : 1 : 1) ternary chelates, MAL where, M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}; L = 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzoxazole (HPBO) and A = glycine, alanine, proline and histidine have been studied pH-metrically in aqueous-dioxane (50% v/v) medium at 30 °C and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength. The formation constants of the complexes were evaluated. The relative stabilities of the ternary complexes were expressed in terms of the parameter $\Delta \log K$ and various factors influencing the formation and stability of complexes are discussed. The thermodynamic parameters (ΔH , ΔS and ΔG) associated with the ternary systems were also evaluated by determining the formation constants at 20, 30 and 40 °C and 0.1 M KNO₃ ionic strength. All the parameters were found to be favourable for the complexation.

Keywords : Binary chelates, ternary chelates, formation constants, stability, thermodynamic parameters.

Introduction

There has been continuous interest in the study of transition metal complexes¹ with potential ligands. The 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzoxazole is a potential (N,O⁻ donor) ligand with analytical and other applications². The amino acids are also well known potential ligands with numerous applications. In the present communication, we report pH-metric equilibrium study of transition metal binary chelates, ML and ML₂ and ternary chelates, MAL where, M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II}; L = 2-(2-hydroxyphenyl)benzoxazole (HPBO) and A = glycine (Gly), alanine (Ala), proline (Pro) and histidine (Hist) in aqueous-dioxane (50%

v/v) medium at 20, 30 and 40 °C and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength.

Results and discussion

Binary systems :

The formation constants of the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 binary complexes of M-HPBO were determined by analyzing the experimental data and titration curves and are listed in Table 1. The stability of the binary complexes follow the order, ML > ML₂. This order of stability can be due to the statistical factors³. The acid-dissociation constants (pK_a) of ligands and the formation constants of the other

Table 1. Acid-dissociation and metal-ligand formation constants of binary complexes in 50% (v/v) aqueous-dioxane medium at 30°C and ionic strength (μ) = 0.1 M (KNO₃)

Ligand	Acid dissociation constant		Co ^{II}		Ni ^{II}		Zn ^{II}	
	pKa ₁	pKa ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K ₂
HPBO	-	11.21	7.61	6.77	7.91	7.37	7.96	7.17
Gly	2.36	9.57	4.64	-	5.78	-	5.30	-
Ala	2.30	9.69	4.31	-	5.40	-	5.60	-
Pro	2.41	10.38	5.10	-	5.95	-	5.65	-
Hist	6.07	9.08	6.90	-	8.67	-	6.55	-

Values are accurate to ± 0.05 .

binary complexes, MA were redetermined under present experimental conditions and listed in Table 1.

Ternary systems :

From the titration curves, the formation of ternary chelates, MAL were found to occur in two different ways.

(i) The complexes, MAL where, A = Gly, Ala and Pro were found to form in single step/simultaneous equilibria.

In these complexes, the ternary complex curve occurs at low pH region than the binary complex, MA and ML curves indicating simultaneous coordination of both the ligands to the metal ion.

(ii) The complexes, MAL where, A = Hist were formed in stepwise/two step equilibria.

In these complexes, the ternary complex curve overlap with the binary complex, MA curve in the lower pH region, indicating the formation of binary complex in the first step. Later, the divergence of the ternary complex curve from the binary curve, MA at higher pH region indicates the formation of ternary complex, MAL in the second step. Thus, in these complexes the ligand, L (HPBO) acts as a secondary ligand.

In all the cases, distinct inflections were observed in the titration curves, indicating the nature of complexation. The formation of ternary complexes were also confirmed from other observations such as change in intensity of colour of the complexation medium, shift in pH of precipitation etc., compared to the corresponding binary complexes. The species distribution curves generated for some representative systems (Figs. 1 and 2) using the computer program, BEST⁴ also supports the formation of

ternary chelates at higher pH-region.

The formation constants of ternary chelates were evaluated and presented in Table 2. The relative stabilities of the ternary complexes compared to the corresponding binary complexes were characterized in terms of the statistical parameter, $\Delta \log K$ and are presented in Table 2, where,

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{MAL}^M - \log K_{MA}^M - \log K_{ML}^M$$

or

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{MAL}^M - \log K_{ML}^M$$

For better correlation, the stability per unit base strength (SUBS)⁵ of the ligand also evaluated and listed in the same table. The formation constants (Table 2) indicate that all the ternary complexes formed are fairly stable. The negative values of $\Delta \log K$ indicate that the formation of ternary complexes is less favoured than the corresponding binary complexes. This can be due to the statistical factors³. From the results, it can be observed that the stabilities of the ternary complexes, MAL with respect to the ligand, A follow the order :

This order of stability is in accordance with the basicity of these ligands as also supported by SUBS values. The higher stability of Hist systems can also be due to the Π - Π (stacking) interaction⁶ of the ligand A and L.

The stability of the complexes, MAL with respect to the metal ion follow the natural⁷ order : $\text{Co}^{II} < \text{Ni}^{II} > \text{Zn}^{II}$.

The thermodynamic parameters associated with the ternary chelates were evaluated and listed in Table 3. The negative values of enthalpy (ΔH) indicate that the formation of ternary chelates is exothermic in nature.

Fig. 1. Species distribution curves of Ni^{II}-Hist-HPBO ternary system.

Fig. 2. Species distribution curves of Co^{II}-Gly-HPBO ternary system.

Table 2. Formation constants of M^{II}-A-HPBO ternary complexes in 50% (v/v) aqueous-dioxane medium at 30 °C and $\mu = 0.1 M$ (KNO₃)

A	Co ^{II} -A-HPBO			Ni ^{II} -A-HPBO			Zn ^{II} -A-HPBO		
	log K_{MAL}^M	$\Delta \log K$	SUBS	log K_{MAL}^M	$\Delta \log K$	SUBS	log K_{MAL}^M	$\Delta \log K$	SUBS
Gly	11.79	-0.46	0.568	12.31	-1.38	0.593	11.69	-1.57	0.563
Ala	10.93	-0.99	0.523	11.75	-1.56	0.562	11.37	-2.19	0.544
Pro	12.39	-0.32	0.574	12.62	-1.24	0.585	12.65	-0.96	0.586
Hist	9.63 ^a	+2.03	0.860	9.75 ^a	+1.84	0.871	9.20 ^a	+1.24	0.821

^a log K_{MAL}^M ; values are accurate to ± 0.05 .

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters of M^{II}-A-HPBO ternary complexes in 50% (v/v) aqueous-dioxane medium at 30 °C and $\mu = 0.1 M$ (KNO₃)

A	Co ^{II} -A-HPBO			Ni ^{II} -A-HPBO			Zn ^{II} -A-HPBO		
	$-\Delta G$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta H$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S$ (kcal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta G$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta H$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S$ (kcal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta G$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta H$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S$ (kcal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
Gly	1485.74	149.02	4.41	1511.73	128.53	4.57	1480.61	165.25	4.34
Ala	1440.13	160.69	4.22	1483.69	149.53	4.40	1463.89	169.88	4.27
Pro	1515.63	127.70	4.58	1526.71	139.26	4.58	1528.14	138.93	4.58
Hist	1363.88	164.13	3.96	1371.33	180.04	3.93	1336.37	190.75	3.78

The negative values of free energy (ΔG) and the positive values of entropy (ΔS) indicate that the formation of ternary chelates is spontaneous and entropy favoured.

Experimental

The HPBO was prepared and purified by known procedure⁸. All other ligands and reagents used were of AnalaR (Merck/B.D.H.) grade. The stock solution of HPBO was prepared in 1,4-dioxane and all other solutions were prepared using doubly distilled water. The solutions of metal ions, HNO₃ and KOH were standardized by known methods⁹. The pH-metric titration of 50 ml of acidified solution containing 1 : 1 : 1 (M : A : L) molar solution of ternary systems were carried out against KOH solution in dioxane-water (50% v/v) medium at 20, 30 and 40 °C and 0.1 M (KNO₃) ionic strength. For binary systems a metal-ligand ratio of 1 : 5 was maintained at 30 °C. The proton-ligand (pK) and binary (ML, ML₂ and MA) complex formation constants were determined at 30 °C under present experimental conditions by Irving-Rossotti method¹⁰. The formation constants of the ternary complexes were evaluated¹¹ and refined¹². The pH-metric readings in 50% (v/v) dioxane-water were corrected by the method of Van Uitert and Haas¹³.

The thermodynamic parameters enthalpy (ΔH), entropy (ΔS) and free energy (ΔG) associated with the ternary chelates, MAL were evaluated using standard expressions.

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